

Teacher Education Change In Light to the Expanding Higher Education System In Sudan

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مستخلص

أوضح هذا البحث تطور تعليم "تدريب" المعلمين في السودان بتركيز أكثر على التحولات التي حدثت عقب عام 1994م، كما ناقش المشاكل التي نجمت عن هذه التحولات. اعتمد البحث في مصادره على بحوث بعض الخبراء في مجال تعليم المعلمين، وعلى البيانات الرسمية لوزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي، والمكتب الأكاديمي لكلية التربية - جامعة الخرطوم. إتبع البحث المنهجين التاريخي والاشتقاقي. تمثلت أهم نتائج البحث في أن تجارب تعليم "تدريب" المعلمين قبل 1994م كانت أكثر نجاحاً من تلك التي أعقبت العام 1994م، وأن كليات التربية تواجه مشاكل رئيسة تتعلق بقبول الطلاب وتطوير البرامج وتأهيل أعضاء هيئة التدريس والبنية التحتية. اقترح البحث إنشاء جامعة للعلوم التربوية في كل إقليم من أقاليم السودان لتخطي المشاكل الحاضرة لكليات التربية حتى تستطيع تأهيل معلم يمتلك مهارات معرفية وتربوية عالية.

Abstract

This research explained the development of teacher education "training" in Sudan, with peculiarity to reforms following 1994 and, as well, discussed the problems concerned. It based on research done by some experts in the field of teacher education; and on official data of Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research; and on academic office of faculty of Education University of Khartoum. The research adopted historical and derivational approaches. The main findings were that, the experiences of teacher education prior to 1994 were more successful compared to those pro 1994, and that faculties of education face substantial problems concerning students' admission; programs updating, staff qualifying and infrastructure. The research ultimately proposed the establishment of University of Educational Sciences in each region of Sudan to overcome these current problems in order to produce high calibre teacher.

Key words: Teacher Education, Educational Reform, Educational Professionalism, University of educational sciences

Introduction

Sudan has experienced radical reform in its higher education system since 1994 when the State's policy targeted the expansion of universities in all administrative regions of Sudan. The majority of these universalities started by a faculty for education where by 2017; there were more than 30 faculties of education instead of only three prior to 1994. This policy has transferred the task of teacher education "training" from Ministry of Education to the nominated universities. Due to that change, new challenges were emerged and substantial problems were initiated. Good teacher education produces qualified teachers therefore; Sudan has to strengthen its teacher education system so as to cope with World's challenges and development trends.

The research problem

Sudan has exerted good efforts to educate "train" teachers through various decades. This is because teacher education is essential part in human resources development and policies. The research problem is to review these efforts and to discuss the inherent problems associated with their implementation.

The importance of the research

This could include the following:

- 1- It might be the first research that compares the experience of teacher education in Sudan prior and pro 1994.
- 2- Its emerging results might help into formulation and implementation of proper teacher education in the future.

The research objectives

This research objects to:

- 1- Explain development of teacher education in Sudan, with peculiarity to reforms of 1994.
- 2- Discuss problems concerned with that experience.
- 3- Propose the establishment of universities of educational sciences in each region of Sudan.

The research questions

- 1- What are the prominent characteristics of teacher education in Sudan?
- 2- Does teacher education in Sudan cope with recent World's trends in this field?

Delimitation of the research

Time delimitation includes the period of 1934-2018, while objective delimitation is to review teacher education in Sudan in the light of expanding higher education system.

Theoretical Framework

Teacher education or training refers to “the policies, procedures, and provision designed to equip (prospective) teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviours, and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school, and wider community” (Wikipedia, 2019). It could be also “any formal programs that have been established for the preparation of teachers at the elementary and secondary – school levels” (Britannica, 2019). The role of a teacher is to make informed and intelligent decisions about practice to achieve various outcomes with and for students in their classes. Developing countries face many emerging educational reforms and developments in education including, for example, universalization of primary education, continuing education, education for the world of work, and restructuring secondary education (UNESCO, 1990).

It is world widely agreed that, excellent teacher requires excellent professional development (Tatter, 2019). Literature on preparation of teacher for basic education in the developed world had classified the required standards into development, learning, motivation; educational curricula; educational evaluation; and professionalism (Hanan et al., 2016). The movement of education professionalism, which was born due to deficiencies of classical models of a teacher education (table1), had profoundly affected systems and programs of teacher education. It adopted educational research; promotion of teacher skills and educational practice; critical thinking inside a class; good supervision on teaching practice that links educational research with educational sciences and practice.

International approaches and models in teacher education are many. Some approaches have emphasized provisioning of knowledge; provisioning of educational and behavioural sciences; and importantly emphasised teacher's character. Some others have emphasised the social role of a teacher, merging branches of knowledge to escape problems of subject specialization in secondary education (Alrasheed, 2016). Still, another approach has confirmed integration in teachers' training programs, while the pragmatic approach has considered teacher as a technician who needs solid background in general culture, deep specialization in a subject and attainment of educational skills through apprenticeship. Another last approach has linked the content and objectives of programs with professional requirements and training needs for a teacher. Beside these approaches there were some world models for teacher education including, developmental; behavioural; partnership; humanitarian; behavioural-humanitarian; and academic models, as well as standards-based model; simulation-based model; and research in teaching model. Limitations of conventional approaches used in universities around the globe have prompted significant innovations internationally, including alternative approaches to teacher preparation outside the university (Kitchen and Petrarca, 2016).

Table (1): Differences between professionalism movement programs and classical programs in teacher education

No.	characteristic	Classical programs	professionalism modern programs
1	Type of program	Programs are around a group of courses exist in special field of knowledge with no respect to meeting necessities of education profession	Programs are designed around special knowledge of teaching profession to prepare teachers as professionals.
2	Methods of evaluation of courses	Teaching and offering of courses in separate from each other and each staff member teaches only one course	-Courses are built with complementary form to achieve cumulative building of the concepts of teaching profession. -Two staff members or a group of them contribute into teaching a course.
3	Teaching practice execution	-Repeating and frequenting field training at the end of a program. -Period of teaching practice is short therefore the accepted experience is little. -There is distance between bodies supervising teaching practice	-various chances are given during field training through the program. -teacher/trainer become acknowledged to school's students goodly and accepts the required and enough experience, therefore. - Part-timers and staff members contribute together to apply educational theories and practice them by a student/trainer and therefore there are some courses taught inside school during teaching practice.

World widely, there were four type of teaching practice. Type one required a student/ teacher to stay two days a week in a school within two semesters. Type two stated that a student/ teacher has to stay eight weeks a semester teaching 12 hours in a school without any academic burden in a college. In type three a student/ teacher has to teach two subjects with 12 hours a week and stays all weeks of the second semester in a secondary school. In the fourth type, training took place via micro teaching in a college or experimental school during the first semester of fourth year where two days a week were required, and in the second semester a student/ teacher has to go to teaching practice in a school with a rate of 12 teaching hours.

Source of data and approaches

This research had based on research done by some experts in the field of teacher education, and on official data of academic office of faculty of Education University of Khartoum and Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. The research adopted historical and derivational approaches. There was clear emphasis to faculty of education university of Khartoum in our analysis since it was the first faculty of education in Sudan with an experience of more than half a century in this field.

Teacher training in Sudan before 1994

Teacher education in Sudan dated back to 1902 when "Alorafa" section in Gordon Memorial College was established. Gordon Memorial College mainly targeted training a limited numbers of qualified professional Sudanese to replace Egyptians and Syrians employees in civil service. "Alorafa" section was established to train teachers for primary schools in a two- years period which was raised to four- years by 1906. It admitted those who have successfully completed primary school, which required the establishment of two primary schools in Omdurman¹ and Khartoum. In 1921, Omdurman college for training of female teachers was opened, and by 1934, the "Alorafa" section was transferred from Gordon Memorial College to Eduiem² town where Bakht el Rida³ Institute for teacher training was established. The objectives of Bakht el Rida Institute were to prepare professionally and academically qualified teachers to work in rural primary schools, to train in-service teachers, and to design primary schools' curricula.

¹ **Omdurman:** the third town comprising the capital of Sudan, in addition to Khartoum and Khartoum North. It lies along the White Nile and River Nile. It is known as the national capital of Sudan.

² **Eduiem** was the capital of White Nile Province, 240 km south of Khartoum, on the left bank of White Nile River.

³ **Bakht el Rida** was name of the location of the institute in the eastern part of Eduiem town.

Teacher education in Bakht el Rida Institute was primarily a two phase's program. Firstly, a teacher has to spend a preparatory five years in Mabrouka⁴ primary school and secondly, a one-year training in teaching techniques. In 1936, Bakht el Rida Institute was developed to include three schools and two departments in a four-year session program. The three schools were, firstly a primary school for educating children of Eduiem's residents and to work as a experimental school for curricula and teaching techniques and secondly, a dormitory school for selected students to be educated so as to become teachers for primary schools and thirdly, a rural-type intermediate school. The two departments were the Department of Arabic language and Mathematics for curricula preparation for primary schools, and the Department of Primary and Intermediate schools' training, which was supported by British trainers in science, geography and history. In 1940, the training session was raised to 5 years after completing primary school, and then to six years in 1944 when Intermediate College was opened in Bakht el Rida.

In 1937, Lord De Lauer's committee recommended the establishment in-service educational training institutes (ISETI) in other provinces of Sudan under the umbrella of Bakht el Rida. That had been delayed up to 1948 when Dalang⁵ in-service educational training institute was opened, and then followed by Shendi's⁶ in 1952, and then Maridi's⁷ in 1954, where they ultimately reached seventeen institutes; seven of them were for female teachers education. In 1949, and due to rapid increase in intermediate schools which was not commensurate with increase in teachers, exceeding of untrained teachers over trained ones, and lower educational attainment among students, the Ministry of Education 'Maarif' has launched intermediate school teacher training, through refreshing courses, under the supervision of those former in-service educational training institutes (ISETI) (Mohamdain et al., 2016).

In 1967, the committee headed by Dean of Bakht el Rida looked into the possibility of promoting teachers' institutes and colleges, increase years of study to 4 years and training after intermediate school, promoting standards of primary schools' teachers to equal secondary school graduates academically and exceed them professionally. In 1969, educational ladder was changed to 6+3+3 which targeted excessive preparation of primary school teachers in subjects that used to be taught in intermediate school such as English language and mathematics. Furthermore, first year's school subjects in former secondary school were dropped to intermediate school. To cope with these challenges, in-service training, and night training for teachers were activated. A major consequence of educational ladder of 1972 was increasing number of untrained teachers. That has been solved by establishment of more in-service educational training institutes (ISETI). They targeted continuous training of teachers, strengthening a teacher's self-teaching techniques, responding to teachers' needs that obliged by new curricula, raising a teacher's professional standards (Ali, 2004). The in-service teacher training in these institutes had enabled the Ministry of Education to train teachers without leaving their schools, subjecting a trainer to experimental and applied teaching concepts and thoughts during his daily work, enhanced type of education a teacher could give to his students, providing a good chance to invigilate, guide and counsel each trainer while working in his school, customized a trainer on self-teaching techniques, enabled training of big numbers of teachers. These institutes, with 73 branches were weaved in 1992 and later in 1994, they became programs of bachelor of basic education in faculties of education.

Sudan has experienced secondary school teachers' education in 1961 when the Higher Teacher Training Institute (HTTI) was established jointly by UNESCO and Ministry of Education 'Maarif'. The objectives of HTTI, in addition to filling the gap in provisioning qualified higher secondary schools teachers' to meet wide expansion in secondary education, were to qualify university's graduates in teaching, improving standards of in-service secondary schools teachers, accepting self trust and capacity building in teaching practice and educational research to a student/teacher (Ismail, 1973). The HTTI was affiliated academically to University of Khartoum in 1968, and completely merged by 1974 to become the first faculty of education in Sudan. Some other faculties of education were established in Gezira University, Juba University and Omdurman Islamic University. They mainly objected to qualify teachers with bachelor degree in education and a academic subject for entry into secondary school teaching. The degree awarded developed form a

⁴ Name of a village lies close to Bakht el Rida institute.

⁵ Dalang is a name of a town in Nuba Mountain, western Kordofan state.

⁶ Shendi: a town lies north of Khartoum, nearly 180 km, on the right bank of the River Nile.

⁷ Maridi: a small town lies in former south Sudan, now the Republic of South Sudan following secession in 2011.

diploma in education (1961-1971) by the H.T.T.I to a general degree of education and two subjects (1972-1981), and then to bachelor of science/arts and education - general degree (1982-1988) with a major subject and a minor subject. In the period 1989-2000, in addition to awarding a general degree in education and two subjects, the honours degree was introduced for selective student to study a fifth year and specialize in one subject.

Reforming teacher education in Sudan: 1994-on

The national comprehensive strategy of 1994 and the quarter-century strategy of general education in Sudan stressed on teacher training to achieve higher academic, professional, and behavioral competences for teachers (Abushanab, 1993), which required searching one's and others' experiences in teachers education (Ali, 2004), and the establishment of new faculties of education in all states of Sudan (Figure 1). The conference on educational policies recommended the bachelor degree as the basic requirement for entry to basic education teaching (Khalifa et al., 1990) and kindergarten education as prerequisite for entry to basic school. When primary and intermediate schools were merged together in 1994 to form the basic education school, faculties of education took the responsibilities to train basic education teachers, as well as secondary education teachers. Great effort has been exerted to benefit from Open University of Sudan to qualify in-service teachers and UNESCO initiatives on training of trainees to work in the future in teachers training institutes. The sending of teachers to faculties of education, instead of the former teachers' institutes, faced some obstacles particularly that a teacher stayed away from his family and the high cost of a teacher training. Consequently, less than 10,000 teachers were trained by these faculties during 9 years. This gave a justification to cline teachers training to Open University of Sudan to award all those who have satisfied the requirements for the award of the degree of bachelor of education. Open University of Sudan started admission with 4500 student in 2003, raised to 12,000 in 2004, and rapidly raised to 90,000. That number has dropped down because Ministry of Finance failed to pay training cost to that university (Mohamed, 2009).

Figure 1: States of Sudan

Types of Programs

There are two types of academic programs in the faculties of education. The first one is bachelor in science/arts and education with honours (one subject) to prepare secondary education teachers. The second type is bachelor in education with honours (two subjects) to prepare basic education teachers. In some Sudanese regional universities there is only one program for basic education with honours degree. These faculties have inherited their programs from the mother faculty (Faculty of Education-University of

Khartoum). That faculty used to award during 2000-2007 honours degree in four-year study with specialization into two subjects. That was abandoned by 2007 reform program when all students stayed for five years and finally graduated with honours degree in one subject. That was also applied for basic education program, except that a student specialised into two subjects. By 2017 a new reform program was introduced for basic education program where a student graduated with one subject but, before that he has to study all subjects for six semesters to meet the requirements for a general teacher and a specialized teacher in one subject. The majority of Sudanese faculties of education applied the same programs.

Preschool education teacher training

Programs on preschool education are offered by 10% of Sudanese governmental universities and less than 5% of private universities which award either bachelor degree or a diploma (Gada et al., 2016). These universities apply both integrative and complementary system of preschool teacher education. Preparatory programs emphasis the social role of a teacher; integration between preparatory programs; adoption of pragmatic approach; enhancement of experimental experiences; applying system analysis; and target educational standards. The components of preparatory programs are cultural (known as university requirements), academic (subject specialization), and educational ones (professional subjects). University requirement subjects include Arabic Language; English language, religious education and study skills, sociology and civilization and environmental studies. These subjects constitute small percent of the total credit hours of the program compared to specialized and professional subjects. Specialized subjects include preschool education; lingual development of a kindergarten's child; arithmetic and scientific concepts; child literature; athletic education; child and society health; playing psychology; art education; music and songs. Professional subjects cater for scientific bases of preparatory program; activity design; toys making; educational technology; evaluation techniques; and strategies of child education and training

Universities have established their own kindergartens for teaching practice and gave enough weight for manual training and great concern to selective courses to provide students with base knowledge on a child's art skills; knowledge growth; sensual - mobility growth; social growth; emotional growth; lingual growth and individual differences. Universities also, emphasised the role of a teacher to develop innovation and self-learning skills for children and help them expressing themselves by speech; action; music or drawing. Therefore, child art and literature occupied central part in these preparatory programs.

Basic education teacher training programs

The progressive development of basic education teacher preparation programs could be exemplified by those of faculty of education university of Khartoum which covered the period 1994- 2017. The program of 1994-2007 prepared a teacher into two-subject: mathematics and science; English language and history; Arabic language and Geography; and so on. The total credit hours for graduation were 160. In 2007 a reform program was implemented with two-subject specialization and 170 total credit hours. Teaching practice has been given 10 credit hours. There was no micro teaching or peer group teaching, only teaching in a basic school for one semester (9th semester). In 2017 a new reform program was implemented with 175 credit hours (table 2). The student has to stay five semesters to be prepared as a general teacher capable to teach in the first and second circle of basic education (1-6 year level). In the 6th semester a student has to go to do teaching practice in these two circles, and then returns back to college to stay two semesters studying only one subject so as to become specialized teacher in the third circle (7-8 year level) of basic school. In the 9th semester a student returns back to a basic school to practice teaching in the third circle teaching either mathematics; English language; Arabic language; science; geography and so on. The reform program of 2017 has raised credit hours and split teaching practice into two semesters to achieve requirements for a general and specialized teacher preparation. Beside subject specialization, student has to study university and cultural requirements courses (table 2).

Table (2): Graduation requirements according to semesters and credit hours, Faculty of education, university of Khartoum academic reform for basic education programs (2017)

Stage	Level	Semester	Graduation requirements combined with credit hours/ semester				Total Credit hours
			University requirements	Academic requirements (base)	Educational requirement And activities	Specialization requirements	
General teacher	First	first	6	10	4	-	20
		second	6	10	4	-	20
	Second	first	6	8	4	-	18
		second	2	10	8	-	20
	Third	first	-	16	9	-	25
		second	-	-	6	-	6
	Teaching practice in first and second circles in school (general teacher)						4
Total credit hours			20	54	4+35= 39	-	113
Specialization (Specialised teacher)	Fourth	first		-	8	12	20
		second		-	6	12	18
	Fifth	first	Teaching practice in third circle in basic school (specialized teacher)				4
		second			8	12	20
Graduation total credit hours			20	54	65	36	175

Source: Academic reform program of 2017, faculty of education university of Khartoum

Among faculties of education clear variations existed in subject specialization; credit hours for academic and educational and cultural preparation (Samia et al., 2016). Programs prepared a general and a subject teacher. Although major and minor subject specialization provided teachers for basic education, however, it negatively influenced knowledge attainment of major subject specialization because there was comprehensiveness of academic preparation for major and minor specialization. Some colleges did not care about ideal periods as a necessary condition for qualifying a teacher for teaching practice in a school (Samia et al., 2016). There was weak cooperation and coordination between colleges of education; insufficient time for teaching practice; evaluation process concentrated only on knowledge attainment and solely depended on recitation and clearing which represented the lowest level in knowledge; and there were few activities programs; and training programs for staff members to use educational technology means were similarly scarce (Samia et al., 2016).

Secondary education teacher training

The main features of the applied program in the faculty of education university of Khartoum were that the least number of semesters a student attended were ten with 170 credit hours and specialization in only one subject. One could derive from Hanan et al.'s study (2016) that the ranges of university requirements in universities of Khartoum; Sudan for Science and Technology; Omdurman Islami; Gezeira; Zaim Azhari; Gadariief; Kordofan; and west Kordofan were 18-29 credit hours with a mean of 24.6, while the academic requirements ranges were 90-115 credit hours with a mean of 102.6, and educational requirements ranges were 36-67 credit hours with a mean of 46.8. Great variation existed in credit hours for academic preparation which ranged between 90-115 credit hours where the highest rate was recorded in Zaim Azhari university (110-114) followed by Geziera Hantoub (115-90) and Kordofan (111); Sudan university of science and technology (110) while it ranged between 90-95 in universities of Khartoum, Omdurman Islamic, and Gadariief consecutively. Similarly, variations existed in cultural preparation which was 29-25 credit hours in universities of Zaim Azhari, Omduran Islamic, west Kordofan and Khartoum consecutively; while it was 24 credit hours in Kordofan and Gadariief universities, 23 in Gaziera Hantoub and less than 18 in Sudan university for science and technology. Clear closeness was observed in credit hours for educational preparation which ranged between 40-46 credit hours, except in Geziera Hantoub College⁸ of education which was 67 credit hours because it applied comprehensive type of a teacher preparation, while the least credit hours (36) were recorded in Zaim Azhari University.

⁸ Some universities names a college and some others name a faculty concerning education, see guidebook for admission of students to higher education institutions.

Teaching Practice

Teaching practice in faculty of education, university of Khartoum objected to qualify students to practice real teaching; contribute effectively into daily activities in schools; and to develop personal skills of patience and enthusiasm, for example, which are necessary for teaching profession. The period was one semester (9th semester) with 10 credit hours before 2016. Following 2016, the period was split into two parts with 10 credit hours. The first part was micro teaching and peer teaching with 4 credit hours in the 7th semester. The second part was 6 credit hours for teaching practice in a school in the 9th semester. The unit of teaching practice, which affiliated to department of curricula and teaching methods, in collaboration with other departments in the faculty; schools' administrations; and educational administrations was responsible of the job. The basic requirements were the success in all educational courses, particularly special teaching and general teaching methods courses; with cumulative score of 2.0 a student has to get after completing 4th year (8th semester) in the faculty and at least 100 credit hours completed. Ten students per supervisor, no registered courses, and whole week stay in a school with at least 8 school periods per week and maximally 15 school periods per week were required. Responsibilities of a student/trainee included complete complying with school's timetable and activities; building good relations with school's teachers and administration, the students and their fathers; putting exams and tests; explicating good behaviour and appearance; participating in periodical meetings; avoiding physical punishment and solving students' problems; cooperating with a supervisor, applying what learnt in faculty; self-assessing of own work and promoting skills of teaching; optimizing benefit of available resources into teaching; and recommending and proposing how to develop and promote teaching practice in the faculty from his experience.

Differences into teaching practice characteristics among some Sudanese faculties of education were shown by table (3). They differed into time period; credit hours; number of visits per student; number of evaluation forms used; number of supervisors per student; contribution of general education administrations; and budget per student. In addition, there was weakness in final evaluation mechanisms; supervisors from general education treated student/trainers as if they are expert teachers and evaluated them without any prior directions. Furthermore, there was no care for training courses for schools' administrators and supervisors about methods of teaching practice; no continuous following up for student/trainer; limited budgets to satisfy with the requirements; no updating of teaching practice programs although there were many issued recommendations from conferences and seminars held here and there.

Comparing these local programs with international and regional ones depicted that they lacked behind into preparation, planning, and following up of teaching practice; had no written objectives; number of visits were less when they reached to more than 7-10 visits/semester in international and regional ones, and the number of supervisors/ student are quite few.

Table (3): Teaching practice characteristics among some Sudanese faculties of education

Name of university	University		
	Khartoum	Sudan for Science and Technology	Dalang
Time period	1 semester	2 months	Two semester
Credit hours	5	6 hours	6 hours
Number of visits/student	2/3	3	Two
Number of forms (evaluation)	2	4	Two
Number of supervisors/ student	2	3	Two
General education contribution	Moderate	Positive	Moderate
Budget/ student	100-150 Sudanese pound	250 Sudanese pound	Calculated by credit hours

Source: Niamat Hussien Alhassan (2006)

Problems of teacher education in Sudan

Research done by Educational Studies Committee (2008) and Ali, (2005) had revealed major problems facing teacher education in Sudanese faculties of education. They were use of classical teaching methods; no enhancement of self-learning skills; retarding academic evaluation; no innovation; no entry interviewing tests and skills measurement tests; poor educational research and community service programs; inample time for professional and subject specialization; lower academic scores in Sudanese certificate of the admitted students; prevalence of master degree holders among staff members beside, outside migration of qualified ones. In addition, there were absence of in-service professional training; improper teaching practice and inadequate financial budgets per student; beside cooperation with educational administrations

and community organizations was almost very limited. Programs lacked updating, had no relations with school books or syllabus of general ministry of education, did not comply with the ideal model of faculty of education proposed by ministry of higher education and scientific research which worked according to a program system rather than on a faculty system which opposed with many faculties of education which applied separate programs each in a separate faculty.

Concerning problems in basic education in these faculties, Samia et al.(2016) indicated to no updating of programs; great variations in credit hours for academic and professional preparation, absence of tied links among faculties of education themselves and with ministries of general and higher education, lacked behind in academic evaluation; unobvious wish of students to become teachers; poor infrastructure; major subjects were somehow influenced minor ones; some faculties did not own separate departments when they were a program in a faculty of education. These problems were somehow matched with those of secondary education when the study by Hanan et al. (2016) indicated to that, the objectives of programs were general and ambiguous without specific operational objectives and conformity in meaning and sentencing; beside that, there were no strategic objectives. Credit hours of cultural and professional requirements were almost similar, except in the Geziera and Zaim Azhari Universities when they recorded higher (90-115 credit hours), and that cultural preparation which lacked updating, didn't accept a student the required lingual skills. These programs were also alienated from applied sides; evaluation techniques were weak; laboratories, experimental rooms, lecture rooms, halls, and libraries were ill-equipped; as well as imbalanced ratio of students per teaching staff; no educational counselling; and overburden of administrative duties on the majority of teaching staff. The perspectives of educational administrations on teacher education for general education depicted that, preschool education program satisfied well with requirements of that level, however, basic education programs were poor particularly for the first circle in a basic school, and similarly secondary school teacher programs lacked updating (Fathia and Abdelsadig, 2016).

Teaching practice problems were well shared in many Sudanese universities. Most of the objectives of teaching practice in Sudanese faculties of education were classical ones, focusing more on academic competences rather than on professional and educational ones, and the role of ministry of general education was quite limited. There was no concern of faculties of education on teaching their students social skills accompanying academic training; and in most of the faculties there was no separate department for teaching practice but there were coordinators changing from time to time.

According to Souad (1993) there was absence of an entitled office for following up of teaching practice; lecturing type of teaching influenced on a trainee performance; and there was no unified evaluation form for a trainee. Similarly, Nasreldin (2004) indicated that trainees lacked skills to produce educational means; peer-teaching and micro-teaching training were limited; no guidebook, no prior choice of suitable schools; ignorance of weekly meetings between trainees and supervisors, taking academic load in a college during teaching practice; inconformity between what a trainee learnt in class and what he did during teaching practice; no permanent follow up office, no allowance for a trainee to participate in non academic activities in a school; distribution of trainees in far remote schools, huge numbers of trainees per a supervisor, and a trainee's evaluation did not depend solely on teaching skills. In addition, ill-equipped micro teaching labs, few supervisory visits; crowdedness of lecture rooms; few credit hours for teaching competences; few qualified staff for teaching professional courses; lack of technological aids were quite evident. Dependence on one supervisor per a trainer; interferences of duties of departments participating in teaching practice; absence of transportation means; and weak interactions of schools' administrations with trainers reduced supervision effectiveness. Also, many governmental schools looked to trainers as unqualified for teaching. Poor environment of training schools and shortage of offices allocated for trainers negatively influenced on effectiveness of meeting discussion between a trainee and his supervisor. Importantly, some universities' administrations did not allocate enough budgets and ignored the importance of teaching practice and its role in training and qualifying of student/teacher.

Giving practical examples of some faculties of education might support these results. The experience of Zaim Azhari University in teaching practice confirmed the ignorance of trainees' wish to choose a school to do teaching practice due to insufficient spaces to meet with huge demand of other trainees from other universities, beside the duration was short. In International University of Africa experience there was ill performance of some trainees, lesson planning and time management and use of educational audio-visual

aids were poor, as well as existing difficulties in communication with teachers and students and the duration was short (Isameldin, 1998). Omdurman Islamic University experience matched quite well to that of International University of Africa, but added to that there were ill communication between a school and a faculty and no transportation means to and from a school for a trainee (Rawda, 1999). The Geziera University experience depicted that a trainee' skills on lesson planning and application of explanatory lessons were weak; and continuation lessons were done moderately; students lacked capacity to put evaluation questions and ignoring multiple techniques of evaluation (Mohamed, 2000).

Discussion

Sudan has witnessed two experiences into teacher education, one before 1994, and a second since 1994. Our discussion will explore the real situation of Sudanese faculties of education so as to evaluate failure or success of the pro 1994 reforms. This will include admission of students, programs implemented, staff qualifications, and infrastructure. The enrolment of students in higher education institutions has witnessed a rapid increase due to governmental policies of expansion in number of universities to meet the increase in population and demand for higher education in the country. In the academic year 2017/2018 it was planned to enrol 103,983 thousands with an increase by 6.83% of the preceding academic year (Result of general enrolment 2017/2018). From that total of the students admitted there was 15.02% of them went to faculties of education. Females constituted 66.59% and males 33.31% which meant that for every three female students there was one male student. Due to these policies, the number of students increased annually where during 2010-2015 around 60,000 students were added to these faculties by a percent of increase of 75%. In addition, faculties of education enrolled 31% of the special chairs put for the students of the less developed regions of Sudan, who were enrolled with lower scores in Sudanese secondary certificate. These standards contradicted world standards of admission of students which included a higher score in a secondary certificate, and passing personal interview and skill tests (Alkandary, 2002) as in Japan for example (Aldamanhoury et al., 2000), as well as medical, physical fitness and psychological tests, loyalty to teaching profession, exist of professional development skills, and the ability to pass exam of teaching license, enthusiasm to teaching. Sudanese faculties of education lacked these world standards, in addition to lacking specified tests to reveal tendencies of the applicant to choose his subject specialization (Abdelgawad et al., 1999), and tests on responsibilities, emotional and social balance, leadership, cooperation, self trust, flexibility and communication and knowledge about teaching ethics (Apple, 1990 (Kerka, 1998).

In all Sudanese universities, the highest number of students enrolled went to faculties of education. The example of faculty of education university of Khartoum gave a picture for that, where 21.51% of the total students enrolled in the University of Khartoum in the academic year 2017/2018 went to faculty of education, compared with 0.92% in Forestry College, 1.53% in Animal Production College, and 2.76% in Architecture College. The majority of those enrolled in faculties of education were females who had increased from 56.1% in 2010/2011 to 64.72 in 2015/2016 (Result of general admission 2017/2018, p.9).

There were variations between faculties of education in percentages of admission of students. It reached to a difference of 25% between faculty of education university of Khartoum (75% +) and some other regional faculties, such as faculty of education in University of Duain (50%), in East Darfur. Comparisons between faculties of education in old universities (established before 1994) were not as much as that. They ranged between 15-10% as that in the Geziera University (60-70) and Sudan University for Science and Technology when compared with faculty of education university of Khartoum. Added to that, differences existed between subject specializations. Arts subjects' specialization recorded higher than Sciences and ranged 20-30% between old and regional universities. This had reflected on number of graduates according to specialization where 72.82% of the graduates from the bachelor of basic education faculty of education university of Khartoum were in Arts subjects compared to Sciences in the period 2013-2016 (Academic office, faculty of education, university of Khartoum, 1017).

The academic status of staff members in these faculties skewed towards holders of masters' degree where they represented 48.40% in 2011 and 38.88% in 2015. The percentage of those in the status of assistant professor was 42.25% in 2011 and 40.18% in 2015 (Alredaisy, 2018). They both constituted 90.56% in 2011 and 79.06 in 2015. The percentage of those who were either associate professor or a professor was lowest. However, that was not the case for all those faculties. Those who were either masters' degree holders or

assistant professor were more found in the new faculties of education. Prevalence of masters' degree holders who work as lecturers in these faculties had much negative implication on teaching performance, communication with students, academic counselling, supervision of postgraduate students and scientific research, particularly when they have to register for a PhD. Generally, females exceeded males by 4.31%, for example in 2014. These indications did not conform to demography of Sudan where the ratio of males to females was 51:49 in 2008 (Statistics department 2008). On educational considerations, this will influence employing of teachers where the percentage of female teachers in basic education was 62% and in secondary education it was 54.2% (UNESCO, 2014). Furthermore, employing a teacher sometimes required staying away from a family in a far remote rural area where females cannot afford and opposed Sudanese traditions and norms.

Connecting number of staff members with number of students gave ratios of 1:167 in 2011, 1:98 in 2012 and 1:101 in 2014. Females were more lecturers than being assistant or associate professors compared to males. These figures did not show those who went to work outside or inside Sudan and their geographic distribution. The staff members concentrated more in faculties of education in regional big towns and Khartoum the capital of Sudan where the percent of staff members in faculty of education university of Khartoum represented 6% from the total staff members in all these faculties (Alredaisy, 2018).

Concerning infrastructure of these faculties, the majority were established on the wrecks of old intermediate or secondary schools, except the old ones, which were build since colonial era or after independence of Sudan in 1956. They lacked built standard educational environment of laboratories, lecture rooms, halls, staff offices and green landscape. These influenced quality of teacher education and helped to create an environment of violence among students as was recorded in many of these faculties.

Findings

The main findings of this research are that:-

- 1- Basic teacher education before 1994 has developed under the umbrella of Ministry of General Education and was influenced by governmental policies which worked to cope with internal social changes and demand for education, and with the international environment. That experience was considered successful by all experts.
- 2- Basic teacher education since 1994 has completely become a university type of education, without any ties with policies of Federal Ministry of Education. That experience was considered unsuccessful by many experts.
- 3- Secondary teacher education started under the administration of Ministry of General Education (H.T.T.I for example) up to 1974, and then developed under Sudanese universities. That experience was considered successful before 1994, and unsuccessful pro 1994.
- 4- Faculties of education face erratic problems concerning student admission; academic programs updating, staff qualifying and infrastructure.

Recommendations

One could recommend that Sudanese faculties of education have to:

- Apply selective standards for students' admission, and adopt one academic program including professional and knowledgeable competences.
- Establish smart schools to become experimental labs so as to promote professional competences of students.
- Train teaching staff members abroad.

The question arises here is that: Are these faculties able to deal with these some possible recommendations? The answer is **No**. The reasons are that, these faculties occupied inferior position among other faculties in any of the Sudanese universities and now there is a loud voice calling to abandon them and alternatively adopting the successive type of teacher training where a university graduate has to spend one year study in a diploma of education to qualify him/her for teaching position.

However, regardless of that, these faculties could wake up within our proposed strategy of the **specialized universities** where the **University of Educational Sciences** is pivot. This strategy does not oppose with world's trends where in many countries there are specialized universities for medicine, agriculture, and

engineering for examples. University of Educational Sciences is that university which basically work to qualify teachers through recognized colleges for kindergartens, basic education, secondary education, graduate college and specialized educational research centres to work in collaboration with governmental authorities, civil organizations, and international organizations such as UNESCO. On the own view of the author, this will enable faculties of education to have adequate governmental financial budgets, formulate proper policies of admission of students, update academic programs; promote educational research. These will inevitably enhance the trend of professionalism of teaching in Sudan.

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